

SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS AND MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE SOLVENT CLEANING PROCESS

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Abstract: The use of various models and methods in modern production enterprises is becoming more and more a requirement of the times. In this article, by creating a mathematical model of the "Solvent Cleaning Process" system, the experiences gained on choosing a suitable structure for the process are presented.

Keywords: classification, cleaning, compression ratio, humidity, pressure, pressing, oilcake, solvent, extractor;

The driving force of the compression process is the pressure generated in the press. The degree of compression depends on the nature of the pressure increase, its maximum value, and the duration of the pressure applied to the material. The pressure in the press is determined by the properties of the finished product. For complete extraction of oil, the properties of tension and plasticity are taken into account.

When pressing low-plastic (dried) pulp, the separated oil moves towards the exit of the press, and the pressed material separates in the form of a dry, coarse, high-fat flour-like mass or cake. Therefore, an increase in pressure is observed. Oilcake with high plasticity (highly moistened) does not take the form, but separates as a shapeless, plastic mass. The separating oil moves towards the material arrival. In this case, a decrease in pressure is observed. Thus, the properties of plasticity formed during the roasting process are the main factor determining the value of the pressure generated in the press. Effect of compression level. As a result of pressing, the volume of the dough

decreases due to the separation of oil, compaction of particles, evaporation of moisture and densification of the material [1].

Figure 1.1. Dependence of the degree of compression of the pressure at different moisture levels: $W_3 > W_2 > W_1$ -moisture level.

The duration of pressing, in turn, depends on the geometric shape of the pipe, the speed of rotation of the shaft, the size of the exit slot, the nature of the movement of the material in the press, the properties of tension-plasticity and other factors. The time for dividing the pressed material in each section of the press is determined by the following formula:

$$\tau = V_E + \delta E_c / V_{\min} (1 - \beta), \quad (1)$$

Here:

τ - is the time the material is in the press section,

V_e – volume of free space, m^3 ;

E_c - is the degree of compression in the given part of the press;

V_{\min} - the volume of the press coming to the press for one minute; m^3/\min ;

β - is the coefficient that takes into account losses in the previous section of the material press.

Calculation of the total energy consumption of cottonseed meal is given below :

Total energy consumption (TEC) in food units is calculated according to the following formula :

$$TEC = \frac{1,501*P+2,492*J+1,152*AEM}{1000} \quad (2)$$

Here : AEM - Retention of extractives without azone , g/kg, calculated by the formula :

$$AEM = 1000 - (P + J + Z + K_1) \quad (3)$$

P - mass fraction of crude protein;

J - raw fat mass percentage;

Z- mass fraction of ash;

K₁ -mass portion of raw material;

Before starting the extractor, all main valves that supply water to the condenser are opened. The ejector and cooling machine are turned on and its freezing is checked. After emptying the solvent heater of water and air, the steam inlet valve is gradually opened. It is heated for 5-10 min. Then fresh solvent is fed to the heater. When the water tank is full of solvent and a narrow stream (jet) appears, and the last pump circulating the micelle is full of solvent, the solvent is delivered to the extractor. After the micellar collector capacity is full, the micellar drive pump is turned on. This prevents the solvent from getting to the transport elements. The extraction is started only when the height of the material in the hopper reaches 1.4 m and all the micellar collecting tanks are filled with solvent . As the extractor cells are successively filled, circulation pumps are activated which spray the solvent into these cells through a nozzle.

Total amount of mineral and organic impurities and dust removed:

$$S_2 + T_2 = \frac{100 [(S_0 + T_0) - (S_1 + T_1)]}{100 - (S_1 + T_1)} = \frac{100[(0,35 + 1,07) - (0,15 + 0,53)]}{100 - (0,15 + 0,53)} \\ = 0,745\%$$

Amount of mineral and organic impurities removed:

$$S_2 = \frac{100(S_0 - S_1) + S_1(S_2 + T_2)}{100} = \frac{100(0,35 - 0,15) + 0,15 \cdot 0,75}{100} = 0,201 \%$$

Amount of seed removed:

$$T_2 = (S_2 + T_2) - S_2 = 0,75 - 0,20 = 0,55 \%$$

The composition of the oilcake coming to peel:

$$L_3 = L_0 - T_2 = 43,42 - 0,55 = 42,87 \%$$

The composition of waste in oilcake:

$$C_3 = \frac{C_1 * C_4}{100} - \frac{0,15 * 40,0}{100} = 0,06 \%$$

Oilcake output without taking into account moisture loss during production:

$$L_4 = \frac{100(L_3 - L_2) + L_2(S_2 - T_2)}{100 - (L_2 + Ya_2 + S_3)} = \frac{100(42,87 - 16,0) + 16,0 * 0,75}{100 - (16,0 + 0,64 + 0,06)} = 32,4 \%$$

Oilcake moisture in seeds:

$$B_8 = \frac{100 * V_0 - Ya_1 * V_3}{L_1} = \frac{100 * 10,60 - 56,25 * 8,6}{43,75} = 13,17 \%$$

The output amount of oilcake, taking into account moisture:

$$L_5 = L_4 \frac{100 - V_8}{100 - V_2} = 32,38 \frac{100 - 13,17}{100 - 11,6} = 31,8 \%$$

The amount of output of the Forpress port:

$$J = \frac{[10000 - 100(M_0 + B_0 + L_5 + T_2 + S_2)] + L_5(M_1 + V_2)}{100 - (M_2 + V_1)} + \frac{T_2(M_5 + V_2) + S_2 * V_1}{100 - (M_2 + V_1)} = \frac{[10000 - 100(20,0 + 10,6 + 31,73 + 0,75)] + 31,73(1,5 + 11,6)}{100 - (10,0 + 5,5)} + \frac{0,55(3,10 + 11,6) + 0,2 * 10,6}{100 - (10,0 + 5,5)} = 48,7 \%$$

Output amount of shot:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Sh &= \frac{[10000 - 100(M_0 + B_0 + L_5 + T_2 + S_2)] + L_5(M_1 + V_2)}{100 - (M_3 + V_5)} + \\
 &+ \frac{T_2(M_5 + V_2) + S_2 * V_1}{100 - (M_3 + V_5)} = \\
 &= \frac{[10000 - 100(20.0 + 10.6 + 31.73 + 0.75)] + 31.73(1.5 + 11.6)}{100 - (1.1 + 10.0)} \\
 &+ \\
 &+ \frac{0.55(3.10 + 11.6) + 0.2 * 10.6}{100 - (1.1 + 10.0)} = 46,32 \%
 \end{aligned}$$

The amount of residual oil in the Forpress cylinder:

$$M_6 = \frac{J * M_2}{100} = \frac{48,73 * 10,0}{100} = 4,87 \%$$

Amount of oil loss with shot:

$$P_1 = \frac{Sh * M_3}{100} = \frac{46,32 * 1,4}{100} = 0,648 \%$$

with oilcake

$$P_2 = \frac{L_5 * M_1}{100} = \frac{31,73 * 1,45}{100} = 0,46 \%$$

with empty seed

$$P_3 = \frac{T_2 * M_5}{100} = \frac{0,55 * 3,10}{100} = 0,01705 \%$$

Total estimated output of oil

$$P_1 = M_0 - (P_1 + P_2 + P_3) = 20,00 - (0,51 + 0,48 + 0,02) = 18,9 \%$$

Output amount of Forpress oil

$$P_2 = M_0 - (M_6 + P_2 + P_3) = 20,00 - (4,87 + 0,48 + 0,02) = 14,63 \%$$

Output amount of extraction oil

$$P_3 = P_1 - P_2 = 18,99 - 14,63 = 4,36 \%$$

Amount of moisture loss

$$\begin{aligned} P_5 &= V_0 - \frac{Sh * V_5 + L_5 * V_2 + T_2 * V_2 + S_2 * V_1}{100} = \\ &= 10,6 - \frac{46,32 * 10,0 + 31,73 * 11,6 + 0,2 * 10,6 + 0,55 * 11,6}{100} = \\ &= 2,202 \% \end{aligned}$$

Summary

The main task is to develop the Information Communication Systems-based control structure of the technological system consisting of the solvent cleaning system. An extractor's engineering calculation and a mathematical model of the process, which is considered the main element of the technological system, were developed. Mathematical description of the studied object was found. Furthermore, choosing the method of solving the system of mathematical equations and introducing it in the form of a modeling program, as well as determining the similarity (adequacy) of the model to the object were developed. In the development of a fully representative mathematical model of the process of solvent cleaning of oilcake, the law of phase change in an interconnected three-stage system was analyzed

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